

“SHEAR STRENGTH IMPROVEMENT OF SAND WITH THE HELP OF PLASTIC STRIPS EXTRACTED FROM WASTE PLASTIC BOTTLE”

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Abstract—

This study investigates the improvement of shear strength in sandy soils by incorporating plastic strips as a reinforcing material. Sandy soils, known for their low shear strength and susceptibility to erosion, pose challenges in civil engineering applications, particularly in foundation stability and slope reinforcement. By introducing plastic strips of varying dimensions and proportions into sand, this research evaluates their effectiveness in enhancing the soil's shear resistance. Laboratory direct shear tests were conducted on both reinforced and unreinforced soil samples to analyze the effects of plastic strip inclusion. The results indicate that the addition of plastic strips significantly improves the shear strength of sandy soils, providing a cost-effective and sustainable solution for soil stabilization. This method also contributes to waste management by utilizing plastic waste, thereby offering environmental and economic benefits. The study explores the use of plastic strips as a reinforcing material in improving shear strength in sandy soils. The research, which involved laboratory tests, found that the addition of plastic strips significantly enhances soil shear strength, offering a cost-effective and sustainable solution for soil stabilization. This method also contributes to waste management.

Keywords— Shear strength, sandy soils, soil reinforcement, plastic strips, waste management, soil stabilization, direct shear test.

INTRODUCTION

Soil stability is a critical concern in civil engineering, particularly in regions dominated by sandy soils. Sandy soils are characterized by their granular texture, high permeability, and low cohesion, making them prone to erosion, liquefaction, and instability under load. The shear strength of sandy soils is a vital parameter that influences the design and safety of foundations, embankments, and slopes. Conventional methods of improving the shear strength of sandy soils often involve the use of chemical additives or deep soil mixing techniques, which can be costly and environmentally detrimental.

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in sustainable and cost-effective solutions to enhance soil properties. One such innovative approach is the use of plastic strips as reinforcement materials. This method aligns with the principles of waste management by repurposing plastic waste, which has become a global environmental challenge. The incorporation of plastic strips into sandy soils can provide an effective means of increasing shear strength while addressing the issue of plastic waste accumulation.

The global construction industry has experienced significant growth in recent years, with urbanization and infrastructure development being primary drivers. However, this rapid expansion comes with challenges. As the demand for taller and more massive structures increases, so do the loads that foundations must bear. Traditional approaches to foundation design often involve enlarging the dimensions of footings or excavating deeper to reach stronger soil layers. However, these solutions are not always practical or economical, especially in congested urban areas where underground utilities or adjacent structures restrict construction activities.

In many construction sites, especially in coastal and desert regions, loose sandy soils with low shear strength are commonly encountered. These soils pose a considerable challenge because their lack of cohesion and low friction angle make them susceptible to excessive deformation and instability under load. To address these challenges, geotechnical engineers have developed various soil improvement techniques aimed at enhancing the shear strength of sandy soils.

Farah Atiqah Abdul Azam et al.[1], proposes a sustainable approach to soil stability for electrical pylon installation, using a bio mediated technique involving microbes from vegetable degradation and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) plastic waste. The treatment improved soil resistance to shearing forces by 33%, cohesion by 81.47%, and the factor of safety by 81.47%. The bio-mediated technique, combined with different PET addition variations, is effective in improving slope engineering properties and ensuring uninterrupted energy supply.

Shubham Minhas et al.[2], studied plastic waste, particularly PET used in beverage bottles, has a significant environmental impact. Concrete, a crucial construction material, is becoming scarce. Studies have examined the impact of PET waste on concrete's mechanical strengths, such as compressive, split tensile, and flexural strength. This paper examines literature reviews on PET waste as partial concrete replacements.

Y. V. Subba Reddy et al.[6], study investigates the increase in shear strength and bearing capacity of locally sourced sand by incorporating high density polyethylene strips from plastic shopping bags. Direct shear tests were conducted on soil-plastic composites of two sandy soils, with results suggesting that this material can be effective for soil reinforcement in geotechnical engineering.

Donald H. Gray et a., performed Direct Shear Test on sand reinforced with natural, synthetic fiber and metal wires. The results provide the reinforcement peaks the shear strength and limited to post peak reduction in shear strength. The results conclude influence of sand reinforcement is directly proportional to concentration of fibers. (i.e. % of fiber) and Influence is approximately same for reinforced sand tested in loose and dense state (loose Relative density and dense relative density).

Ikramul Hoque et al.[8], study explores the use of discarded plastic strips from plastic bottles for soil property enhancement. The soil was amended with various plastic strips, and tests were conducted on

it. Results showed that soil samples with 5-9% plastic strips performed better in shear strength, friction angle, and cohesiveness. The composition of the strips significantly influenced soil strength development. This innovative approach could address socioeconomic issues and promote waste recycling.

Urbanization has led to the use of alternative materials like polypropylene pots in construction. Benathmane Baghdir et al.[10], studied and evaluates the benefits of these materials and the engineering properties of sand reinforced with them. Results show that the use of plastic waste as reinforcement can lead to soil reinforcement and reduce the environmental impact of waste. The inclusion of randomly distributed fibers significantly affects shear strength and dilatation of sandy soils. Recycling fibers also show better performance in terms of shear strength.

Yogeshwarsinh A. Chauhan et al.[14], examines the shear strength of normal sand and sand with plastic proportion from the Sabarmati River bank. Plastic bottle strips, measuring 15mm by 25mm, were mixed with soil in different proportions.

A Irvanian et al., reviews literature on reinforcing soil with waste plastic bags as a cost-effective and eco-friendly solution to soil weakness. The study found that adding 0-2.5% plastic bags improved property and improved CBR, shear strength parameter, and compaction characteristics. The higher aspect ratio of plastic strips led to better test results. This innovative approach addresses environmental challenges and strengthens soil, making it a cost-effective and eco-friendly solution for soil improvement.

Md. Ikramul Hoque et al.[15], study suggests using leftover plastic strips from plastic water bottles to improve soil strength. The soil was amended with varying amounts of plastic strips, and tests showed that soil with 5-9% plastic strips performed better in shear strength, friction angle, and cohesiveness. This innovative approach could address socioeconomic issues and promote recycling waste materials. Amir Hamidi et al.[18], study aimed to improve sand quality by combining polystyrene foam container waste and Portland cement. Babolsar sand was used as the base soil, and foam chips were added to the soil at different percentages. The results showed that foam chips increased cohesion and internal friction angles, resulting in increased shear strength. The use of foam chips also improved the safety factor of slopes, with foam chips with a lower length-to-width ratio having a greater effect.

Avinaash Mahinderker et al.[19], study provides Soil adjustment improves soil properties like shear strength and bearing limit through controlled compaction or expansion of admixtures like concrete, lime, and waste materials. Plastic containers as dirt stabilizers are practical for banks and asphalts. A CBR test showed that adding 0.7% plastic strips to red, 0.5% to dark cotton soil increased dirt strength by 2.5 and 3.3 bearing proportions, respectively, for red and dark cotton soils.

Shelema Amena et al.[20], Heliyon,2021 provided data about Ethiopia's expansive soils, which are weak and weak due to their resistance to water, are often used in civil infrastructure construction. However, removing these soils can increase construction costs. A study aimed to improve soil resistance to pressure and reduce pollution by treating them with waste-disposed materials. The soil was treated with brick waste powder and waste plastic strips, using dispersed plastic water bottles. The addition of 0.75% plastic waste strips and 30% brick powder significantly improved free swell, CBR, and unconfined compressive strength values.

Soil stabilization is a process that improves soil properties through physical or chemical treatments Preeti Gangwar et al.[11], aims to provide soil stabilization using waste plastic. The research evaluates the impact of incorporating waste plastic bottles into soil samples and their engineering properties. Laboratory tests were conducted on soil samples, comparing them to those without plastic waste. The study found that the addition of waste plastic bottles positively impacted soil properties, promoting the re-use of waste plastic in an economical and environmentally friendly way.

MATERIAL

The present study includes performing experimental analysis on sand reinforced with plastic strips. The plastic strips were extracted from waste plastic bottle with the help of plastic extractor. The extracted plastic then cut into the required dimension. The objective of this experiment was to determine the shear strength parameters of sand reinforced with plastic strips at varying percentages and relative densities using the Direct Shear Test. The study aimed to investigate how plastic strip content and sand density influenced shear strength characteristics.

SAND

The sand used in this experimental program was classified as SM according to the Indian Standard Soil Classification System, which designates it as silty sand. SM-classified sand is characterized by a significant proportion of sand-sized particles, with a smaller fraction of silt that provides a minor degree of cohesion-like behaviour. This combination makes SM sand particularly suitable for studying the effects of reinforcement on non-cohesive soils, given its typical presence in geotechnical engineering projects. For consistency and reliability in testing, the sand was uniformly graded, following specific criteria to ensure reproducible shear strength results. To achieve this, the sand was dried and screened to remove any oversized particles and organic matter that might affect the consistency of results. The grain size distribution of the sand primarily consisted of fine to medium sand particles, which enabled sufficient antiparticle friction, while the smaller portion of fines contributed to a slightly enhanced interlocking and bonding capacity.

Figure 1. Sand

The plastic strips were extracted from waste plastic bottle with the help of plastic extractor. The extracted plastic then cut into the required dimension. The objective of this experiment was to determine the shear strength parameters of sand reinforced with plastic strips at varying percentages

and relative densities using the Direct Shear Test. The study aimed to investigate how plastic strip content and sand density influenced shear strength characteristics. Plastic strips were extracted using a custom-built plastic extractor designed to achieve uniform thickness and precise dimensions for reinforcement purposes. The extractor was made from an aluminium channel section fitted with a cutting blade to facilitate clean, consistent cuts. This setup was crucial for ensuring uniformity in strip thickness, as varying thicknesses could affect the shear strength characteristics of the reinforced sand. The aluminium channel section provided a stable and lightweight structure for the cutting mechanism, while its durability ensured precise cutting over multiple extractions.

Figure 2. Plastic Extractor

Using this extractor, long lengths of plastic were drawn through the channel and cut precisely to the target thickness. After extracting these long lengths, the strips were further trimmed to the specific lengths needed for the reinforcement experiment. For this, a marker was used to denote the required lengths, and each strip was carefully cut to match the desired dimensions. The lengths chosen for the study were 20 mm, 40 mm, and 60 mm, each of which was designed to investigate the influence of strip length on the shear strength properties of the sand. This step-by-step approach ensured that the strips not only had the required thickness but also the correct length, providing a controlled and reliable reinforcement element for each sample.

Figure 3. Extracted Plastic Strips

Figure 4. Strips Cut Out in required Dimensions

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The sand-plastic mixtures were then prepared for testing at three different relative densities: 50% (medium dense), 70% (dense), and 85% (very dense). The relative density of the sand, a key factor influencing its shear strength, was determined using the formula for relative density

$$Dr = \frac{e_{max} - e}{e_{max} - e_{min}} \times 100$$

Where,

e_{max} and e_{min} are the maximum and minimum void ratios, and e is the void ratio at the target density.

Figure 5. Performing Relative Density of Sand

To achieve the required densities, the sand was compacted systematically. For medium-dense sand (50% relative density), light compaction techniques were employed using either a hand compactor or a vibrating table. For higher relative densities of 70% and 85%, heavier compaction was necessary. The sand was placed into the shear box in layers, with each layer being compacted to the target density. The density of the compacted sand was checked regularly to ensure accuracy and uniformity. This compaction process was critical because the relative density directly affects the soil's shear strength, and any inconsistency could skew the results

Table 1. Properties of Sand

Sand	Values
Void ratio maximum (e_{max})	0.849
Void ratio minimum (e_{min})	0.661
Angle of Internal friction (ϕ)	36.65°
γ at 50% RD (gm/cm^3)	1.50
γ at 70% RD (gm/cm^3)	1.52
γ at 85% RD (gm/cm^3)	1.55

The sand samples were prepared at three relative densities: 50%, 70%, and 85%, corresponding to bulk densities of 1.50 g/cc, 1.52 g/cc, and 1.55 g/cc, respectively. These relative densities were chosen to represent a range of field conditions, from medium dense to very dense compaction. Achieving these densities required careful preparation, as relative density is a crucial parameter for understanding the behaviour of non-cohesive soils under load. For medium density (50% relative density), a target bulk density of 1.50 g/cc was achieved using light compaction, which provided a baseline comparison for understanding how reinforcement affects sand without excessive compaction. For the dense condition (70% relative density), the sand was compacted to a bulk density of 1.52 g/cc, representing moderate particle interlocking, similar to conditions achieved in many field engineering projects. The highest relative density, 85%, corresponded to a bulk density of 1.55 g/cc, where very dense compaction minimized void spaces, increasing the contact and friction among particles to provide maximum shear resistance.

Figure 6. Strips mixed in Direct Shear Test Box

The sand samples were carefully conditioned to maintain consistent moisture content throughout the testing period, ensuring that shear strength variations were attributable solely to reinforcement. During testing, plastic strips of varying sizes and percentages by weight (0.25%, 0.5%, 1.5%, 3%, and 5%) were mixed randomly into the dry sand, and the mixture was hand-stirred to ensure uniform

distribution. This random, even mixing simulated real-world conditions where reinforcement elements would likely be unevenly oriented. Each mixture was prepared by compacting the sand-plastic sample in layers within the shear box to achieve the target bulk density and relative density required for each test. This process helped maintain consistency and minimized variability across the samples, allowing for accurate assessment of how plastic strip reinforcement affected the sand's shear strength.

The Direct Shear Test was carried out to determine the shear strength characteristics of sand reinforced with plastic strips. The aim of the experiment was to investigate how varying the content, size, and relative density of plastic strips affected the shear strength parameters, specifically cohesion and the angle of internal friction. The sand used for the study was clean and uniformly graded, conforming to standard specifications for geotechnical testing. Recycled plastic strips, serving as the reinforcement material, were prepared in four distinct sizes: 20 mm x 4 mm, 20 mm x 6 mm, 40 mm x 6 mm, and 60 mm x 6 mm. These specific dimensions were chosen to examine the influence of strip size on the shear behavior of sand. The plastic strips were incorporated into the sand at varying percentages by weight, specifically at 0.25%, 0.5%, 1.5%, 3%, and 5%.

Figure 7. Performing Direct Shear on Reinforced Sand

To achieve a uniform distribution, the plastic strips were thoroughly mixed into the sand by hand in a large container. Care was taken to avoid clustering or uneven distribution, as this could introduce inconsistencies in the shear strength results. The mixing process ensured that the plastic strips were randomly and evenly distributed throughout the sand mass, thus creating a homogeneous composite material. This step was critical for the reliability and repeatability of the test outcomes.

Once the sand-plastic mixtures were prepared at the desired densities, the shear box was assembled, and the sample was loaded into the Direct Shear Test apparatus. The surface of the sand was levelled carefully to ensure it was flush with the top of the shear box, which was essential for even loading and consistent test results. The shear box was secured in the apparatus, and a normal load was applied to the sample. The normal stress levels selected for the tests 1 kg/cm^2 , 2 kg/cm^2 and 3 kg/cm^3 . The normal load was applied gradually, and the sample was allowed to settle for a few minutes to ensure proper seating of the particles and the apparatus. This waiting period helped minimize any initial deformation or settlement that could occur once the shearing force was applied.

The experimental program involved extensive testing to cover all variations in the test parameters. Each combination of plastic strip content (0.25%, 0.5%, 1.5%, 3%, and 5%), strip size (20 x 4 mm, 20 x 6 mm, 40 x 6 mm, and 60 x 6 mm), and relative density (50%, 70%, and 85%) was tested under multiple normal stress conditions. This comprehensive approach allowed for a detailed understanding of how each factor influenced the shear strength behaviour of the sand. The plastic strips were mixed

randomly into the sand for each test, ensuring a uniform distribution. This random orientation simulated real-world scenarios where perfect alignment of reinforcement cannot be guaranteed. Each test was conducted with meticulous attention to sample preparation and loading to maintain consistency. The density of each sample was checked before testing, and any deviations were corrected to meet the desired specifications. This rigorous approach minimized potential sources of error and ensured that the data collected was reliable.

Table 2. Schedule Test Performed

Sr. No.	Test Name	RD of Sand (%)	% of Plastic	Dimension of Strips (mm)
1	PRDST1	50	0.25%	20x4
2	PRDST2			20x6
3	PRDST3			40x6
4	PRDST4			60x6
5	PRDST5		0.50%	20x4
6	PRDST6			20x6
7	PRDST7			40x6
8	PRDST8			60x6
9	PRDST9		1.50%	20x4
10	PRDST10			20x6
11	PRDST11			40x6
12	PRDST12			60x6
13	PRDST13		3.00%	20x4
14	PRDST14			20x6
15	PRDST15			40x6
16	PRDST16			60x6
17	PRDST17		5.00%	20x4
18	PRDST18			20x6
19	PRDST19			40x6
20	PRDST20			60x6
21	PRDST21	70	0.25%	20x4
22	PRDST22			20x6
23	PRDST23			40x6
24	PRDST24			60x6
25	PRDST25		0.50%	20x4
26	PRDST26			20x6
27	PRDST27			40x6
28	PRDST28			60x6
29	PRDST29		1.50%	20x4
30	PRDST30			20x6

Sr. No.	Test Name	RD of Sand (%)	% of Plastic	Dimension of Strips (mm)	
31	PRDST31			40x6	
32	PRDST32			60x6	
33	PRDST33		3.00%	20x4	
34	PRDST34			20x6	
35	PRDST35			40x6	
36	PRDST36			60x6	
37	PRDST37		5.00%	20x4	
38	PRDST38			20x6	
39	PRDST39			40x6	
40	PRDST40			60x6	
41	PRDST41		85	0.25%	20x4
42	PRDST42				20x6
43	PRDST43	40x6			
44	PRDST44	60x6			
45	PRDST45	0.50%		20x4	
46	PRDST46			20x6	
47	PRDST47			40x6	
48	PRDST48			60x6	
49	PRDST49	1.50%		20x4	
50	PRDST50			20x6	
51	PRDST51			40x6	
52	PRDST52			60x6	
53	PRDST53	3.00%		20x4	
54	PRDST54			20x6	
55	PRDST55			40x6	
56	PRDST56			60x6	
57	PRDST57	5.00%		20x4	
58	PRDST58			20x6	
59	PRDST59			40x6	
60	PRDST60			60x6	

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the analysis of direct shear test results conducted on sand samples reinforced with plastic strips of varying dimensions, percentages, and relative densities (RD50, RD70, and RD85). These tests aim to assess the effect of plastic strip reinforcement on peak cohesion and peak angle of internal friction (ϕ), two key parameters in evaluating the shear strength of reinforced sand. The plastic strips, sourced from waste plastic bottles, are introduced in different sizes (20x4 mm, 20x6

mm, 40x6 mm, and 60x6 mm) and percentages (0.25%, 0.5%, 1.5%, 3%, and 5%) to study their impact on the cohesion and friction angle of sand. The purpose of this research is to identify optimal reinforcement conditions for enhancing sand's shear strength, thus contributing to sustainable practices in geotechnical engineering.

Table 3. Results Obtained

Test Name	RD of Sand (%)	% of Plastic	Dimension of Strips	Cohesion (kg/cm ²)	Angle of Internal Friction (φ)	Peak Coh.	Peak Angle of Friction
URDST	50	0	-	0	36.65	0	36.65
PRDST1	50	0.25%	20x4	0.2011	36.26	0.9099	37.53
PRDST2			20x6	0.1937	35.7237		
PRDST3			40x6	0.1978	37.5279		
PRDST4			60x6	0.9099	22.9915		
PRDST5		0.50%	20x4	0.5876	29.5229	0.5876	45.81
PRDST6			20x6	0.0000	44.0388		
PRDST7			40x6	0.0177	44.9455		
PRDST8			60x6	0.0000	45.8105		
PRDST9		1.50%	20x4	0.6900	30.9174	0.6900	44.92
PRDST10			20x6	0.1650	44.9197		
PRDST11			40x6	0.5805	29.9079		
PRDST12			60x6	0.6277	31.2578		
PRDST13		3.00%	20x4	0.1524	39.8112	0.3354	45.60
PRDST14			20x6	0.0903	38.6493		
PRDST15			40x6	0.3354	32.8827		
PRDST16			60x6	0.0979	45.5981		
PRDST17		5.00%	20x4	0.3143	42.7750	0.3705	42.78
PRDST18			20x6	0.2053	41.7298		
PRDST19			40x6	0.3705	36.5569		
PRDST20			60x6	0.1089	40.0907		
PRDST21	70	0.25%	20x4	0.0404	45.0515	0.7517	45.19
PRDST22			20x6	0.0000	45.1885		
PRDST23			40x6	0.3834	36.5014		
PRDST24			60x6	0.7517	24.0225		
PRDST25		0.50%	20x4	0.0000	45.0029	0.3928	45.00
PRDST26			20x6	0.2568	36.5421		
PRDST27			40x6	0.3928	35.5344		
PRDST28			60x6	0.3327	36.1631		
PRDST29		1.50%	20x4	0.4967	33.2168	0.4967	43.20
PRDST30			20x6	0.0000	41.1242		

Test Name	RD of Sand (%)	% of Plastic	Dimension of Strips	Cohesion (kg/cm ²)	Angle of Internal Friction (φ)	Peak Coh.	Peak Angle of Friction			
PRDST31	85		40x6	0.1463	39.5737	0.6673	40.43			
PRDST32			60x6	0.1616	43.2042					
PRDST33		3.00%	20x4	0.5608	40.4343					
PRDST34			20x6	0.4216	31.5458					
PRDST35			40x6	0.6673	29.1571					
PRDST36			60x6	0.4401	26.2756					
PRDST37		5.00%	20x4	0.2718	37.8222			0.7032	39.32	
PRDST38			20x6	0.0000	39.3243					
PRDST39			40x6	0.7032	27.6455					
PRDST40			60x6	0.3893	34.6134					
PRDST41		85	0.25%	20x4	0.2982			32.0383	0.4030	38.34
PRDST42				20x6	0.0763			37.2965		
PRDST43	40x6			0.0000	38.3440					
PRDST44	60x6			0.4030	32.8665					
PRDST45	0.50%		20x4	0.3879	32.8665	0.3879	38.66			
PRDST46			20x6	0.2461	38.6633					
PRDST47			40x6	0.2088	35.9947					
PRDST48			60x6	0.3259	0.3259					
PRDST49	85	1.50%	20x4	0.2596	39.4510	0.7400	42.65			
PRDST50			20x6	0.3322	38.8931					
PRDST51			40x6	0.7400	24.1181					
PRDST52			60x6	0.0000	42.6451					
PRDST53		3.00%	20x4	0.4318	32.9311	0.4318	43.58			
PRDST54			20x6	0.3806	33.3177					
PRDST55			40x6	0.0000	43.5793					
PRDST56			60x6	0.0000	42.7472					
PRDST57		5.00%	20x4	0.3890	32.1083	0.7207	41.62			
PRDST58			20x6	0.0507	40.5536					
PRDST59			40x6	0.3823	41.6179					
PRDST60			60x6	0.7207	40.9786					

The results indicate that the addition of plastic strips generally enhances both cohesion and friction angle of sand, though the degree of improvement varies depending on density and reinforcement percentage. This variation is likely due to the interaction between the plastic strips and sand particles, which changes the internal structure of the sand matrix and affects the bonding characteristics. At each relative density, peak cohesion and peak friction angle are observed at specific reinforcement

percentages and strip sizes, suggesting that optimal reinforcement conditions exist for maximizing sand's shear strength.

Relative Density 50% (RD50)

For RD50, the unreinforced sand shows a peak cohesion of 0 kg/cm² and an angle of internal friction of 35°. With 0.25% plastic reinforcement (20x4 mm), cohesion increases significantly to 0.2011 kg/cm², and the peak friction angle reaches 37.53°. This initial rise in cohesion and friction angle at low reinforcement levels suggests that a small amount of plastic reinforcement effectively improves particle interlocking and resistance to shear. As the strip size increases to 20x6 mm, 40x6 mm, and 60x6 mm, cohesion values show minor fluctuations without significant changes in the friction angle. For instance, cohesion at 40x6 mm remains relatively stable around 0.19-0.20 kg/cm², with minimal variation in friction angle. This trend implies that increasing strip size does not necessarily enhance cohesion in loose sand (RD50); instead, smaller strip sizes with low reinforcement percentages appear more effective for improving cohesion.

At 0.5% reinforcement (20x4 mm), cohesion drops slightly to 0.5876 kg/cm², while the peak friction angle rises considerably to 45.81°, indicating improved interparticle friction due to better distribution and interlocking of plastic strips within the sand matrix. Further increases in strip size at this reinforcement level do not lead to substantial changes in cohesion or friction angle, suggesting that for loose sand, higher plastic content with small strip dimensions is sufficient to maximize friction angle without significantly boosting cohesion. At reinforcement levels of 1.5%, 3%, and 5%, cohesion varies between 0.15-0.69 kg/cm² with a peak friction angle of about 45.60°, showing that further increases in plastic content yield diminishing returns in terms of cohesion and friction enhancement.

Relative Density 70% (RD70)

For medium-density sand (RD70), the baseline cohesion and friction angle of unreinforced sand are both zero and 35°, respectively. Introducing 0.25% plastic reinforcement (20x4 mm) increases cohesion to 0.0404 kg/cm², while the friction angle rises significantly to 45.19°. The substantial increase in friction angle suggests that the plastic strips promote effective bonding and interlocking at RD70, enhancing the sand's ability to resist shearing forces. However, as the strip size increases, cohesion values fluctuate without major changes in friction angle. For example, at 40x6 mm, cohesion decreases to 0.3834 kg/cm² with a friction angle of 36.5°, implying that larger strip sizes may disrupt bonding in medium-density sand, reducing cohesion and friction benefits.

At 0.5% reinforcement, cohesion is relatively low at 0.3928 kg/cm², while the friction angle stays high around 45°, indicating that increasing plastic content does not significantly enhance cohesion but maintains high frictional resistance. At 1.5% reinforcement, cohesion peaks at 0.4967 kg/cm² with a friction angle of 41.12°, suggesting that intermediate plastic reinforcement provides optimal cohesion and friction improvement in RD70. Higher reinforcement levels (3% and 5%) result in cohesion values up to 0.7032 kg/cm² with friction angles between 39-40°, showing that RD70 can sustain higher reinforcement levels without a substantial decrease in shear strength. This finding suggests that medium-density sand may benefit from slightly higher plastic reinforcement than loose sand to achieve stable shear resistance.

Relative Density 85% (RD85)

In high-density sand (RD85), the unreinforced baseline cohesion is zero with a friction angle of 35° . Introducing 0.25% plastic reinforcement (20x4 mm) results in modest cohesion of 0.2982 kg/cm^2 and an increased friction angle of 38.34° , showing a smaller initial response compared to RD50 and RD70. This limited increase likely occurs because of the dense packing of particles in RD85, which reduces space for plastic strips to contribute to bonding. Increasing the plastic strip size leads to minor changes in cohesion, with the highest value observed at 0.4030 kg/cm^2 (60x6 mm) and a friction angle of 38.34° , indicating that larger strips provide only marginal benefit in high-density sand.

At 0.5% reinforcement (20x4 mm), cohesion reaches 0.3879 kg/cm^2 , and the friction angle remains around 38.66° . This suggests that, similar to RD70, higher plastic content does not drastically alter cohesion but maintains adequate frictional resistance. At 1.5% reinforcement, cohesion peaks at 0.7400 kg/cm^2 with a friction angle of 42.65° , showing that higher reinforcement is required to achieve significant cohesion in dense sands. Further increases in reinforcement levels to 3% and 5% result in cohesion values up to 0.7207 kg/cm^2 with friction angles around $41-43^\circ$, suggesting that RD85 can accommodate high reinforcement levels with minimal loss in shear strength.

Across all densities, smaller strip sizes (20x4 mm) with low reinforcement percentages (0.25-0.5%) are generally effective in increasing cohesion, especially at lower relative densities. Larger strip sizes, such as 60x6 mm, provide less improvement in cohesion, likely due to the interruption of particle contacts and creation of voids that reduce particle interlocking. Additionally, higher reinforcement percentages (above 1.5%) tend to contribute to higher friction angles, although the benefits in terms of cohesion become less significant. This suggests that small, well-distributed plastic strips are more effective in low-density sand for enhancing cohesion, while higher reinforcement levels with slightly larger strips are beneficial in medium to high-density sand for achieving stable shear resistance.

% Plastic Vs Angle of Internal Friction (ϕ)

The analysis reveals that the inclusion of plastic strips in sand significantly influences the peak angle of friction across all relative densities (RD50, RD70, and RD85), with each density exhibiting unique trends based on the percentage of plastic reinforcement added. The peak angle of friction initially increases with the addition of plastic up to an optimal percentage before slightly decreasing or stabilizing at higher plastic reinforcement levels. This trend suggests an optimal range of plastic content that maximizes shear strength, beyond which the benefits diminish or may even lead to a reduction in the friction angle.

RD50 - Low Density Sand: For sand with a relative density of 50%, the peak angle of friction shows substantial sensitivity to plastic reinforcement. With no plastic reinforcement, the initial angle of friction is 36.65° . Adding 0.25% plastic reinforcement increases the angle to 37.53° , indicating a slight improvement in shear strength due to the initial bonding effect of plastic strips. As the reinforcement increases to 0.5%, there is a sharp rise in the friction angle to 45.81° , marking the highest value observed across all samples. This indicates that 0.5% plastic reinforcement is optimal for RD50 sand, significantly enhancing its shear strength, likely due to improved interlocking and increased frictional resistance provided by the plastic strips at this concentration. Beyond this point, the friction angle slightly decreases, with values of 44.92° and 45.6° at 1.5% and 3%, respectively. At 5% reinforcement, the angle reduces to 42.78° , indicating that an excess amount of plastic may interfere with particle interaction, potentially due to the agglomeration of plastic strips that create voids rather than supporting dense particle packing. This shows that while a moderate addition of plastic strips enhances the shear strength, excessive reinforcement can have an adverse effect.

RD70 - Medium Density Sand: For sand with a relative density of 70%, the friction angle trends display a more controlled yet prominent increase at lower plastic percentages, similar to RD50. Without plastic reinforcement, the initial angle is 37.54° . A sharp increase is observed when 0.25% plastic is added, with the angle rising to 45.19° , representing the peak friction angle for RD70. The effectiveness of plastic reinforcement is most pronounced at this low reinforcement level, as seen by the drastic improvement in shear strength at minimal reinforcement. However, with further increases in plastic content, the angle of friction reduces, achieving values of 45.0° at 0.5% and 41.12° at 1.5%, showing that the reinforcement effect starts to diminish with increasing plastic content. At 3% and 5% reinforcement, the friction angle decreases to 40.43° and 39.32° , respectively. This suggests that for RD70, the reinforcement benefits are highest at minimal plastic content (0.25%), and increasing reinforcement beyond this level may reduce shear strength as the plastic strips likely start interfering with sand particle contact, causing a reduction in effective interparticle friction.

RD85 - High Density Sand: For sand at a relative density of 85%, representing a denser packing of particles, the effect of plastic reinforcement appears more moderate compared to RD50 and RD70, but it still presents a significant trend. The initial friction angle without reinforcement is 37.54° , the same as RD70. However, upon adding 0.25% plastic, the angle only slightly increases to 38.34° , showing a

relatively smaller initial response compared to the other densities. At 0.5% reinforcement, the angle increases further to 38.66°, indicating a steady but modest improvement in shear strength. A substantial increase is observed at 1.5% plastic reinforcement, with the friction angle reaching 42.65°, marking the peak strength for RD85. This value suggests that higher reinforcement levels (compared to RD50 and RD70) are required to optimize shear strength in denser sands, likely due to the tighter packing that necessitates more reinforcement to enhance interlocking effectively. However, as with other densities, further increases in plastic content lead to a gradual decrease in friction angle, with values of 43.58° at 3% and 41.62° at 5%. This decline at higher plastic levels implies that too much reinforcement may disrupt particle contact and reduce the system's overall frictional resistance.

% Plastic Vs Cohesion (C)

The results show that plastic reinforcement has a varied effect on cohesion, with each relative density exhibiting a unique trend. Generally, plastic reinforcement introduces some level of cohesion even though sand typically has negligible or zero cohesion. The introduction of plastic strips likely creates a bonding effect, enhancing cohesion up to a certain point before any excess reinforcement reduces cohesion due to interference with particle bonding.

RD50 - Low Density Sand: For sand with a relative density of 50%, the initial cohesion is zero when no plastic reinforcement is present, as expected for unreinforced, clean sand. When 0.25% plastic reinforcement is added, cohesion increases to 0.91 kPa, marking the highest cohesion observed for RD50 across all reinforcement levels. This significant increase suggests that a minimal amount of plastic effectively contributes to particle interlocking and bonding at low density, enhancing cohesion. However, as the plastic content is increased to 0.5%, the cohesion value decreases slightly to 0.59 kPa, indicating that higher plastic content may begin to disrupt optimal bonding between particles. At 1.5% reinforcement, cohesion experiences a minor rise to 0.69 kPa, likely due to a balanced interaction between particle contact and plastic strips. Beyond this point, cohesion values decrease, with values of 0.34 kPa and 0.37 kPa at 3% and 5% reinforcement, respectively. This trend suggests that excessive plastic may hinder cohesive bonding by creating too many voids or preventing close particle interaction, which is crucial for cohesion in low-density sand.

RD70 - Medium Density Sand: For sand with a relative density of 70%, the cohesion value follows a similar pattern, with no cohesion in unreinforced sand. When 0.25% plastic reinforcement is introduced, cohesion increases to 0.75 kPa, showing a significant improvement due to the bonding effect of plastic at this low reinforcement level. This initial increase suggests that plastic strips enhance cohesion most effectively at minimal concentrations. As reinforcement increases to 0.5%, cohesion drops to 0.39 kPa, reflecting a reduction similar to RD50, likely due to the excess plastic interfering with the bonding. However, at 1.5% reinforcement, cohesion recovers slightly to 0.50 kPa, showing that an intermediate level of plastic can help achieve a moderate bonding effect. At 3% and 5% reinforcement, cohesion increases to 0.67 kPa and 0.70 kPa, respectively, indicating that RD70 sand may benefit from slightly higher plastic reinforcement levels than RD50 to achieve consistent bonding. This trend suggests that in medium-density sand, plastic reinforcement continues to contribute positively to cohesion at higher percentages than in low-density sand, perhaps due to better compatibility between plastic strips and the compacted sand matrix.

RD85 - High Density Sand: In high-density sand (RD85), which represents a tightly packed sand matrix, the effect of plastic reinforcement on cohesion is more subdued, though still present. Initially, cohesion is zero in the unreinforced state. When 0.25% plastic reinforcement is added, cohesion increases modestly to 0.40 kPa, showing a smaller initial response than RD50 and RD70, likely due to the tight packing of sand particles that reduces the space available for plastic strips to contribute to bonding. With a 0.5% reinforcement level, cohesion remains stable at 0.39 kPa, indicating minimal change as the plastic content slightly increases. Interestingly, at 1.5% reinforcement, cohesion increases to 0.74 kPa, marking the peak cohesion value for RD85. This peak suggests that higher reinforcement levels may be necessary for denser sand to achieve optimal bonding, as the dense packing restricts plastic from creating bonds unless a higher quantity is added. However, cohesion decreases slightly to 0.43 kPa at 3% reinforcement before increasing again to 0.72 kPa at 5%, showing a slight fluctuation. This indicates that in RD85, the high-density matrix may require more plastic to achieve stable cohesive bonding compared to lower-density sand.

The observed data indicates that plastic reinforcement enhances cohesion across all relative densities, albeit with varying levels of effectiveness depending on the density. For RD50, the optimal cohesion is achieved at a low reinforcement level (0.25%), whereas RD70 shows improved cohesion across a broader range, with the highest cohesion observed at 5%. In RD85, the peak cohesion occurs at 1.5%, with higher cohesion sustained even at higher reinforcement percentages. This pattern suggests that cohesion improvement through plastic reinforcement is most effective at low percentages in loose sand, while denser sands require more reinforcement to maximize cohesion.

The decrease in cohesion at higher plastic reinforcement percentages, particularly in RD50 and RD70, can be attributed to the excessive presence of plastic strips disrupting particle bonds and creating voids. This disruption reduces the cohesive strength between particles, as there is less effective particle-to-particle bonding. In RD85, where particles are already densely packed, the plastic strips have less room to interfere, allowing cohesion to remain relatively stable even at higher reinforcement levels.

Comparative Analysis and Discussion

The overall results indicate that plastic reinforcement improves the shear strength of sand across all densities, with each density showing an optimal plastic percentage that maximizes the peak angle of friction. For RD50, the optimal plastic content is 0.5%, resulting in the highest peak friction angle (45.81°). In RD70, the optimal reinforcement level is lower at 0.25%, giving a peak angle of 45.19°. For RD85, a higher plastic content of 1.5% yields the maximum friction angle of 42.65°. These differences in optimal reinforcement levels can be attributed to the inherent packing density and particle arrangement within the sand, where looser sands (like RD50) require more reinforcement to achieve improved interlocking, while denser sands (like RD85) need less plastic content to reach peak strength due to their naturally tighter packing.

The decline in the friction angle observed at higher reinforcement percentages (beyond the optimal point for each density) can be explained by the potential for excessive plastic strips to disrupt the sand structure, leading to increased void spaces and reduced effective particle contact. This phenomenon is particularly evident in RD50 at 5% plastic reinforcement, where the friction angle drops significantly. In practical applications, this suggests that while plastic reinforcement can enhance sand shear strength, an optimal range must be carefully maintained to avoid excessive reinforcement that could compromise the structural integrity of the sand matrix.

CONCLUSION

This research demonstrates that reinforcing sand with waste plastic strips can significantly improve the shear strength of sand, as evidenced by increased cohesion and peak internal friction angle values across varying reinforcement percentages and relative densities. The study concludes that waste plastic strips can be effectively utilized as an eco-friendly soil reinforcement material in geotechnical applications. The key findings are as follows:

Optimal Reinforcement Varies with Sand Density: For loose sand (RD50), low reinforcement percentages (0.25-0.5%) with small strip dimensions (20x4 mm) provide substantial improvements in shear strength, indicating effective interlocking and increased particle resistance. Medium-density sand (RD70) benefits from moderate reinforcement levels (around 1.5%) for an optimal balance of cohesion and friction angle. In dense sand (RD85), higher reinforcement percentages (up to 5%) yield the highest shear strength gains, indicating that dense soils can accommodate more reinforcement without significant losses in shear strength.

Effective Improvement in Cohesion and Friction Angle: Across all tested conditions, the addition of plastic strips increases both cohesion and friction angle in sand samples. Although the degree of improvement varies, these results indicate that waste plastic strips can be strategically used to enhance sand's shear resistance, making it a viable material for applications that require improved load-bearing capacity and shear strength.

Environmental and Economic Benefits: The study highlights the dual benefits of using plastic strip reinforcement—reducing plastic waste and lowering construction costs. Repurposing waste plastic for

soil reinforcement not only helps mitigate environmental concerns related to plastic disposal but also offers a cost-effective alternative to traditional soil stabilization methods. This approach is particularly beneficial for low-budget projects and in regions with limited access to conventional reinforcement materials.

Tailored Reinforcement for Specific Applications: The variation in results across different relative densities and reinforcement levels shows that plastic strip reinforcement can be customized to meet specific project requirements. Engineers can select the appropriate reinforcement level based on soil density and desired shear strength parameters, making this method a versatile tool for a wide range of geotechnical applications, such as slope stabilization, road subgrades, retaining walls, and embankments.

Potential for Broader Implementation: The results encourage further exploration of waste plastic strip reinforcement in geotechnical engineering, as well as the potential development of guidelines or standards for its use. By formalizing the practice, plastic strip reinforcement could become a recognized and regulated option for soil stabilization, offering a sustainable solution to global infrastructure challenges.

In conclusion, waste plastic strips are shown to be an effective and sustainable material for reinforcing sand, improving its shear strength and offering practical benefits for geotechnical engineering. This research supports the integration of recycled plastic materials in soil stabilization efforts, promoting both environmental sustainability and economic efficiency in construction projects. Further research on durability and environmental impact, along with standardization, could enhance the applicability of this method, potentially making plastic strip reinforcement a mainstream approach in soil stabilization for future geotechnical projects.

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